

Biota of New Zealand IDs to Wikidata Workflow

Documentation for adding Biota of New Zealand IDs to Wikidata taxon items

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Introduction

Biota of New Zealand (<https://biotanz.landcareresearch.co.nz/>) is both a website and a database providing access to data about plants, fungi and invertebrates found in or associated with Aotearoa New Zealand. This data is maintained by the Manaaki Whenua – Landcare Research Group of the New Zealand Bioeconomy Science Institute. Each record in the Biota of New Zealand database has a unique identifier that also constitutes part of the URL address for that record. This unique identifier assists users of this database to link to the information contained within it.

Editors of Wikidata (https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Main_Page), the knowledgebase sister project for Wikimedia projects, have recognised the importance of the information contained in the Biota of New Zealand database and have wanted to ensure that appropriate Biota of New Zealand identifiers are linked to relevant taxa items within Wikidata. A Wikidata Property “Biota of New Zealand ID” ([P12292](https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Property_proposal/Biota_of_New_Zealand_ID)) was therefore proposed and was subsequently created on the 13th of January 2024. The following link provides an archive of the property proposal and the community discussion on the creation of this property https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Property_proposal/Biota_of_New_Zealand_ID.

Subsequent to the creation of the Biota of New Zealand ID property, work has been undertaken by multiple Wikidata editors to add the Biota of New Zealand ID to appropriate Wikidata items. However, as of January 2026, this task is not yet complete.

This document has been created to encourage and support both Wikidata editors and staff from the Manaaki Whenua - Landcare Research group of the New Zealand Bioeconomy Science Institute to add this identifier to appropriate Wikidata items.

Motivations for adding Biota of New Zealand ID to Wikidata

There are several motivations for undertaking this work. Adding the Biota of New Zealand ID to appropriate Wikidata items assists with the discovery of the Biota of New Zealand website, improves the interconnectedness of the Biota of New Zealand database with other biota databases, and can improve the visibility and reuse of the openly licensed data held in the Biota of New Zealand database.

Internet search engines such as Google and other internet platform companies such as Microsoft use Wikidata to help gather and disseminate information. By adding the Biota of New Zealand ID to Wikidata, editors are helping to empower internet search engines and internet platform companies to provide wider access to up-to-date data on New Zealand's biodiversity. Researchers, policy advisers and makers, conservation groups and natural

history institutions, as well as the general public, are thereby assisted in gaining access to the data held in the Biota of New Zealand database.

Wikidata is not just a data repository. It is also an institutional identifier hub. Wikidata acts as a bridge between one institution's data and another institution's data. Adding Biota of New Zealand identifiers to appropriate Wikidata items ensures the Biota of New Zealand database is semantically linked to multiple other databases, which in turn helps embed the Biota of New Zealand database into the wider biodiversity data ecosystem.

The addition of the Biota of New Zealand identifier to Wikidata items can also help in the discovery, and subsequent correction, of errors in the Biota of New Zealand dataset, as well as in the associated data held on Wikidata items and the data held in the multiple databases linked to those same Wikidata items.

Finally adding the Biota of New Zealand identifier to Wikidata empowers the Manaaki Whenua - Landcare Research group with the potential to enrich the Biota of New Zealand database, either by adding links to appropriate Wikidata items or Wikipedia articles, or by extracting data direct from Wikidata and ingesting it into the Biota of New Zealand database.

Identifiers

Biota of New Zealand ID	Q8P 64a2d14e-66be-49d7-b1c9-c6ca6b03ea75	edit
	▶ 1 reference	
		+ add value
BOLD Systems taxon ID	Q8P 993357	edit
	▶ 1 reference	
		+ add value
Catalogue of Life ID	Q8P 95Z47	edit
	▶ 1 reference	
		+ add value
GBIF taxon ID	Q8P 4702893	edit
	▶ 1 reference	
		+ add value
Google Knowledge Graph ID	Q8P /g/11g6njg8pn	edit
	▶ 1 reference	
		+ add value
iNaturalist taxon ID	Q8P 386103	edit
	▶ 1 reference	
		+ add value
IRMNG ID	Q8P 10049822	edit
	▶ 1 reference	
		+ add value
New Zealand Organisms Register ID	Q8P a15b9e94-ea03-4cc2-8c02-fd2b9403a317	edit
	▶ 1 reference	
		+ add value

Multiple database identifiers listed on the [Wikidata item](#) for the moth *Asaphodes beata*, including the Biota of New Zealand ID and the New Zealand Organisms Register ID. Wikimedia Foundation. [CC BY-SA 4.0](#)

OpenRefine

The workflow set out in this document uses OpenRefine (<https://openrefine.org/>) to bulk upload appropriate Biota of New Zealand IDs into Wikidata. OpenRefine is a powerful tool that can be used to clean, reconcile and ingest data into Wikidata. This document will work through how to extract the Biota of New Zealand ID from the Biota of New Zealand website (<https://biotanz.landcareresearch.co.nz/>), how to add this data to OpenRefine, how to reconcile it against Wikidata genera and species items and finally how to enrich Wikidata taxa items with that identifier as well as with appropriate supporting references back to the Biota of New Zealand website.

Prerequisites for uploading data to Wikidata via OpenRefine

To upload data to Wikidata via OpenRefine the editor will need an [autoconfirmed](#) account, that is a Wikidata account that is more than four days old and with at least 50 edits. The editor must also [authorize OpenRefine with that account](#).

Dataset

This workflow will use genera and species data for the order Lepidoptera downloaded from the Biota of New Zealand website on the 29th of September 2025 as the exemplar dataset.

Screenshot of the Biota of New Zealand Website. Copyright New Zealand Bioeconomy Science Institute. Reused with permission.

Although most current species taxon names have existing items in Wikidata, the Biota of New Zealand dataset also contains original combinations, basionyms and synonyms. It is therefore likely that some species names listed in any downloaded dataset from Biota of New Zealand will need Wikidata items created for them. It is important that Wikidata items for missing taxon names be created in order to achieve the aim of adding the Biota of New Zealand ID to all appropriate Wikidata items.

It is therefore recommended that, when working on a group of species, two datasets be downloaded from the Biota of New Zealand website. The first is a genera dataset and the second is the related species dataset. The reason for this is that some of the taxonomic names within the species dataset are unlikely to have equivalent Wikidata items and these Wikidata items will have to be created.

When creating new Wikidata items for species taxa, the Wikidata taxon data model requires a genus taxon item to be linked to via the “parent taxon” ([P171](#)) property. Editors will therefore need to ensure that appropriate genera Wikidata items exist prior to the creation of new species Wikidata items.

For the basic taxon data model for a species Wikidata item see this documentation https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:WikiProject_Taxonomy/Tutorial#Basic_properties.

Example genera dataset used for this documentation

Link to the Biota of New Zealand search to obtain genera data worked on for this documentation:

<https://biotanz.landcareresearch.co.nz/search?query=order:Lepidoptera&searchType=all&facts=taxonRank:%22genus%22>

Example species dataset used for this documentation

Link to the Biota of New Zealand search to obtain species data worked on for this documentation:

<https://biotanz.landcareresearch.co.nz/search?query=order:Lepidoptera&searchType=all&facts=taxonRank:%22species%22>

Downloading Genera dataset

The first step is to download the appropriate dataset from the Biota of New Zealand website <https://biotanz.landcareresearch.co.nz/>. In order to obtain the data used for this document a search for order:Lepidoptera was undertaken. Then, in the left hand side bar, the search was filtered by “genus”. “Select all” was then ticked. A download button then appeared on the top right hand side of the search. The data was downloaded by pressing the download dataset icon.

BIOTA of NEW ZEALAND
Names and classification of bacteria, fungi, land invertebrates and plants

Manaaki Whenua
Landcare Research

Home | About | Terms of use | Related resources

All records | order:Lepidoptera

All data | Associations

Selected filters
Taxonomic rank: "genus" X

Filters
Metadata
Record class
scientific name (748)
Record source

Results
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 Next
Select all (748 selected) Showing 1 to 100 of 748 records Sort by: Relevance

Achaea Hübner, 1823
Record source: Names_NZAC Added: 08 Mar 2011 Updated: 07 Mar 2016
Animalia > Arthropoda > Insecta > Lepidoptera > Erebidae

Achroia Hübner, [1819]
Record source: Names_NZAC Added: 08 Mar 2011 Updated: 23 Jun 2015
Animalia > Arthropoda > Insecta > Lepidoptera > Pyralidae

Screenshot of Biota of New Zealand website. Copyright New Zealand Bioeconomy Science. Reused with permission.

Download records ✕

Please ensure the record classes you want to download are selected. Then indicate the data standard and file format you require for each class. Refer to the [Help](#) page for further information about downloading data.*

Scientific name

Data standard * BiotaOfNZ BiotaOfNZ-brief NZOR

File format * JSON Tab separated values (TSV) XML

Email address *

Email

This address will be used to send a link to the data you have requested once the download is ready.

Download purpose *

Please indicate the main download purpose for this data to assist us in understanding the use to enable ongoing improvements and reporting.

Systematic or taxonomic research
 Ecological research or biological research
 Biodiversity or biosecurity management
 Education
 Citizen science
 System development or testing
 Other

I accept the [Terms of use](#) **OK** **Close**

Protected by reCAPTCHA and the Google [Privacy Policy](#) and [Terms of Service](#) apply.

Screenshot of Biota of New Zealand website. Copyright New Zealand Bioeconomy Science. Reused with permission.

The above box will then appear. Select the data standard required, in this case BiotaOfNZ, as well as the file format needed. It is recommended the Tab separated values (TSV) format be selected as this ensures the creation of an OpenRefine project is relatively simple. Fill in your email address, the download purpose and read and accept the terms of use (<https://biotanz.landcareresearch.co.nz/terms-of-use>). Then press ok. The dataset will then be generated and emailed to you.

When received, open the sent email and save the data file to the downloads folder on a computer.

Creating the OpenRefine project

The next steps assume the Wikidata editor has OpenRefine installed on their computer. If not, go to <https://openrefine.org/> and install OpenRefine. Then open OpenRefine and create a project for the genus dataset that has just been downloaded. Do this by pressing the “choose files” tab and then select the downloaded Biota of NZ data file. Then press the “next” button.

Screenshot of an OpenRefine showing the “Create project” tab. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

OpenRefine will then show what the project will look like. If satisfied, press “create project”.

OpenRefine A power tool for working with messy data.

Create project « start over Configure parsing options Project name Lepidoptera genera BiotaONZ tsv Tags Create project »

Open project
Import project
Language settings
Extensions

	NameId	NomenclaturalCode	TaxonRank	NameFull	NamePart	Kingdom	Phylum	Class	Order	Family	Genus
1.	002907d6-777c-4278-8b37-c37052b8d4ca	ICZN	genus	Sphenarches	Sphenarches	Animalia	Arthropoda	Insecta	Lepidoptera	Pterophoridae	Sphenarches
2.	00c798c4-3222-427c-adf9-5255e8632ea7	ICZN	genus	Voglia Pastrana, 1961	Voglia	Animalia	Arthropoda	Insecta	Lepidoptera	Pyalidae	Voglia
3.	010965bd-dbbd-490e-88c4-c330d08fdeb8	ICZN	genus	Tachyptilia Heilmann, 1870	Tachyptilia	Animalia	Arthropoda	Insecta	Lepidoptera	Gelechiidae	Tachyptilia
4.	01253ae9-831a-4f21-9f90-79de1c206f03	ICZN	genus	Sperchia Walker, 1869	Sperchia	Animalia	Arthropoda	Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae	Sperchia
5.	01cde081-49ac-4501-a56e-220a08ba2e41	ICZN	genus	Tortrix Linnaeus, 1758	Tortrix	Animalia	Arthropoda	Insecta	Lepidoptera	Tortricidae	Tortrix
6.	0112ffe5-395b-4cf8-8c30-35b7c1766627	ICZN	genus	Ambia Walker, 1859	Ambia	Animalia	Arthropoda	Insecta	Lepidoptera	Crambidae	Ambia
7.	029efa40-1444-4ccb-a19b-606d71cdc7b5	ICZN	genus	Oegoconia Stainton, 1854	Oegoconia	Animalia	Arthropoda	Insecta	Lepidoptera	Autostichidae	Oegoconia
8.	034f0eed-98a4-4cb7-ab02-b8378f8e27c8	ICZN	genus	Vanicela Walker, 1864	Vanicela	Animalia	Arthropoda	Insecta	Lepidoptera	Roeslerstammidae	Vanicela
9.	035831a1-5ccd-4ba7-b133-57f86da5da65	ICZN	genus	Spodoptera Guenée, 1852	Spodoptera	Animalia	Arthropoda	Insecta	Lepidoptera	Noctuidae	Spodoptera

Parse data as Character encoding UTF-16LE Update preview

CSV / TSV / separator-based files

Line-based text files
Fixed-width field text files
PC-Axis text files
JSON files
MARC files
JSON-LD files
RDF/N3 files
RDF/N-Triples files
RDF/Turtle files
RDF/XML files

Columns are separated by
 commas (CSV)
 tabs (TSV)
 custom \t

Use character * to enclose cells containing column separators
 Trim leading & trailing whitespace from strings
 Escape special characters with \

Ignore first 0 line(s) at beginning of file
 Parse next 1 line(s) as column headers
 Column names (comma separated)

Discard initial 0 row(s) of data
 Load at most 0 row(s) of data

Attempt to parse cell text into numbers
 Store blank rows
 Store blank columns
 Store blank cells as

Version 3.9.5 [TRUNK]
 Preferences
 Help
 About

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project showing the preview screen before creation. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](#)

The created project should look similar to the below screenshot.

OpenRefine Lepidoptera genera BiotaONZ tsv Permalink Open... Export Help

Facet / Filter Undo / Redo 0 / 0 754 rows Extensions Wikibase

Show as: rows records Show: 5 10 25 50 100 500 1000 rows « first < previous 1 - 10 next > last »

All	NameId	NomenclaturalCode	TaxonRank	NameFull	NamePart	Kingdom	Phylum	Class	Order
1.	002907d6-777c-4278-8b37-c37052b8d4ca	ICZN	genus	Sphenarches	Sphenarches	Animalia	Arthropoda	Insecta	Lepidoptera
2.	00c798c4-3222-427c-adf9-5255e8632ea7	ICZN	NomenclaturalCode	Voglia Pastrana, 1961	Voglia	Animalia	Arthropoda	Insecta	Lepidoptera
3.	010965bd-dbbd-490e-88c4-c330d08fdeb8	ICZN	genus	Tachyptilia Heilmann, 1870	Tachyptilia	Animalia	Arthropoda	Insecta	Lepidoptera
4.	01253ae9-831a-4f21-9f90-79de1c206f03	ICZN	genus	Sperchia Walker, 1869	Sperchia	Animalia	Arthropoda	Insecta	Lepidoptera
5.	01cde081-49ac-4501-a56e-220a08ba2e41	ICZN	genus	Tortrix Linnaeus, 1758	Tortrix	Animalia	Arthropoda	Insecta	Lepidoptera
6.	0112ffe5-395b-4cf8-8c30-35b7c1766627	ICZN	genus	Ambia Walker, 1859	Ambia	Animalia	Arthropoda	Insecta	Lepidoptera
7.	029efa40-1444-4ccb-a19b-606d71cdc7b5	ICZN	genus	Oegoconia Stainton, 1854	Oegoconia	Animalia	Arthropoda	Insecta	Lepidoptera
8.	034f0eed-98a4-4cb7-ab02-b8378f8e27c8	ICZN	genus	Vanicela Walker, 1864	Vanicela	Animalia	Arthropoda	Insecta	Lepidoptera
9.	035831a1-5ccd-4ba7-b133-57f86da5da65	ICZN	genus	Spodoptera Guenée, 1852	Spodoptera	Animalia	Arthropoda	Insecta	Lepidoptera
10.	0359b5c5-673b-4426-a5cd-5ebf520cc41b	ICZN	genus	Leptocroca Meyrick, 1883	Leptocroca	Animalia	Arthropoda	Insecta	Lepidoptera

Using facets and filters
 Use facets and filters to select subsets of your data to act on. Choose facet and filter methods from the menus at the top of each data column.
 Not sure how to get started?
[Watch these screencasts](#)

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project showing the newly created project. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](#)

Reconciliation

Now the downloaded data is in OpenRefine the editor can start working on the data. The first step is to commence reconciling the dataset data against Wikidata. OpenRefine has the Wikidata reconciliation service built-in and configured by default in its standard installation.

Therefore to start this process scroll along to the genus row.

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project showing the dropdown menu on the genus column. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](#)

Click the dropdown menu on the Genus column, then select “Reconcile” and then “Start reconciling”.

Reconcile column Genus

Select a service to reconcile against:

- Wikimedia Commons (en)
https://commonsreconcile.toolforge.org/en/api
- Wikidata reconcil.link (en)
https://wikidata.reconci.link/en/api
- ORCID
https://refine.codefork.com/reconcile/orcid

Add standard service...

Discover services...

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project showing the selection of the Wikidata reconciliation service. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](#)

Then chose the service to reconcile against. In this case choose to reconcile against Wikidata.

Reconcile column Genus

Reconcile each cell to an entity of one of these types:

- taxon
Q16521
- titular see
Q15217609
- asteroid
Q3863
- town in the United States
Q15127012
- ancient city
Q15661340
- scholarly article
Q13442814
- town
Q3957
- fortification
Q57821

Also use relevant details from other columns:

Column	As property
NameId	<input type="text"/>
NomenclaturalCode	<input type="text"/>
TaxonRank	<input type="text"/>
NameFull	<input type="text"/>
NamePart	<input type="text"/>
Kingdom	<input type="text"/>
Phylum	<input type="text"/>
Class	<input type="text"/>
Order	<input type="text"/>
Family	<input type="text"/>
Species	<input type="text"/>
Authors	<input type="text"/>

Reconcile against type:

Reconcile against no particular type

Auto-match candidates with high confidence

Maximum number of candidates to return

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project showing the types of data that can be reconciled against. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](#)

OpenRefine will then suggest several types of entity to reconcile the data against. As it is a genus dataset, taxon is the type of entity that should be chosen. However if OpenRefine does not list the appropriate type needed the editor can suggest a type by selecting “Reconcile against type:” and adding the type of data to the provided box.

Once the type is selected, press the “start reconciling” tab. OpenRefine will then commence reconciling the data against Wikidata. Depending on the size of the dataset this may take some time.

Reconcile cells in column Genus to type Q16521
 0% complete [Cancel](#)

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project notification while reconciling data. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](#)

OpenRefine will automatically match the data in the uploaded dataset to the appropriate Wikidata item where it is highly confident they are the same. If there is doubt OpenRefine will present reconciliation options to choose from. Where there is no match OpenRefine will give the option of creating a new Wikidata item.

Sphenarches
Choose new match

Vogtia

- [Vogtia](#) (100)
- [Vogtia](#) (100)
- [Vogtia](#) (100)
- [Create new item](#)

[See more](#) | [Search for match](#)

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project showing a reconciled cell and a cell that has not been reconciled. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](#)

In the above screenshot the first genus *Sphenarches* has been correctly matched. The second genus shown, *Vogtia*, has not been matched but OpenRefine has provided potential matches for the editor to consider. Multiple options are provided as there exist Wikidata items for a genus of plants as well as a genus of Cnidaria along with a genus of moth, all with the same name.

Austrotortrix

- [Create new item](#)

[Search for match](#)

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project showing a cell of data where OpenRefine has been unable to find a match on Wikidata. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](#)

If OpenRefine is unable to find a match to a genus name provided by the dataset, it will provide the editor with the option of creating a new item.

Manual reconciliation

Elachista <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Elachista (100) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Elachista (100) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Elachista (100) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Create new item See more Search for match	edit	Treitschke	Treitschke	
Peripyra Choose new match	<div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px;"> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between; border-bottom: 1px solid #ccc;"> Match this cell Match all identical cells Cancel </div> <div style="display: flex; align-items: center;"> <div> <p>Elachista (Q775899)</p> <p>genus of insects</p> </div> </div> </div>			
Hierodoris Choose new match				
Curvisaccula	Dugdale	Dugdale		

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project showing the box generated by hovering the cursor over a selected taxon name. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](#)

Before creating new Wikidata items for the unmatched genera, the editor should attempt to manually reconcile entities in the dataset against their appropriate Wikidata items. Hover the cursor over each OpenRefine suggestion to check whether this is the appropriate item. If needed the editor can click through to the Wikidata item to judge whether the suggestion is the correct item to reconcile against. If correct, press the “match this cell” tab.

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project showing the “Search for match” option. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

If none of the suggestions are correct, the editor should press “search for match” and manually check whether the appropriate Wikidata item is available to reconcile this data against. If no appropriate Wikidata items can be found, the cell should be left unreconciled. Unreconciled cells will be used to assist in the creation of new Wikidata items.

Creating new Wikidata items

Once the Genus column is as reconciled as possible, appropriate unreconciled cells should then have a Wikidata item created for each of them.

Notability

When creating new Wikidata items via OpenRefine the editor should first check whether those proposed new items are suitable for inclusion in Wikidata. For further information on notability for the purposes of Wikidata see <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Notability>.

In the case of the items being created as a result of this workflow, these can be included as they meet the Wikidata notability criteria. Each taxon is a clearly identifiable concept that can be described using serious and publicly available references. Also the creation of these taxa items is fulfilling a structural need as the end goal of this workflow is to add the Biota of New Zealand ID statement to appropriate items in Wikidata.

Genus	Species	Authors	BasionymAuthors	CombinationAuthors
		Pastrana	Pastrana	
		Heimemann	Heimemann	
		Walker	Walker	
		Linnaeus	Linnaeus	
		Walker		

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project showing how to facet the genus column based whether the data in the cells have been reconciled or not. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](#)

In order to work on only those taxa that need new Wikidata items created for them, the Genus column should be faceted to select those taxa cells that are unreconciled. To do this go to the Genus column, press the down arrow and select “reconcile”, then select “Facets” and then select “By judgement” as shown in the above screenshot.

OpenRefine Lepidoptera genera BiotaOfNZ tsv

Facet / Filter Undo / Redo 190 / 190

754 rows

Show as: row

▼ All

☆	🗨	1.	0
☆	🗨	2.	0
☆	🗨	3.	0
☆	🗨	4.	0
☆	🗨	5.	0

Using facets and filters

Use facets and filters to select subsets of your data to act on. Choose facet and filter methods from the menus at the top of each data column.

Not sure how to get started?
[Watch these screencasts](#)

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project showing the Facet/Filter tab on the left hand side of an OpenRefine project. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](#)

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project showing the result of a facet on reconciled data in the genus column of the dataset. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

OpenRefine will then create a box in the Facet/Filter tab on the left hand side of the page giving a summary of the number of cells in the Genus column that have been reconciled and the number that have not.

Go to the lefthand side of OpenRefine and select the Facet/Filter tab, then select those items that have not been reconciled. This is done by including the “none” portion of the dataset. This results in OpenRefine only showing those rows where the taxon name in the Genus column has not been reconciled.

In the below example the unreconciled genera names are now shown. These are the genera taxon names for which a Wikidata item is needed to be created. As each of these new Wikidata taxon items will need to have a “parent taxon” value, the family column in the dataset will also need to be reconciled.

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project showing the reconciliation of taxon names in the cells of the Family against Wikidata. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

Go to the Family column, press the dropdown arrow, select “Reconcile” and “Start reconciling...”.

Genus	Species	Authors	BasionymAuthors	CombinationAuthor
		Bradley	Bradley	
		Meyrick	Meyrick	
		Meyrick	Meyrick	

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project showing the “create a new item for each cell...” selection. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](#)

Once the family taxon name cells have all been reconciled against Wikidata, go back to the Genus column, click the dropdown arrow, select “Reconcile”, “Actions” and then “Create a new item for each cell ...”

This will tell OpenRefine that new items should be generated for the unreconciled cells in the Genus column. OpenRefine will edit the “Genus: judgement” box in the Facet/Filter tab on the lefthand side of OpenRefine to reflect the intention to create new Wikidata items by adding another judgement titled “new”.

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project showing the amended Genus : judgment box. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](#)

Go to the left hand side of OpenRefine in the Facet/Filter tab, double check that only those items that will have a new Wikidata item created for them have been selected

Creating item schema

These proposed new Wikidata items now need a data schema created for them. A data schema in OpenRefine sets out the Wikidata edits that will apply to each selected row of an OpenRefine project.

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project showing selection of the Edit Wikibase schema. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](#)

To create a schema for the new Wikidata items and the data to be added to these new items go to the Extensions Wikibase dropdown menu on the righthand side of OpenRefine. Select "Edit Wikibase schema".

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project showing the newly created Schema tab. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](#)

Clicking this will open a set of new tabs next to the rows tab. These include a “Schema” tab, an “Issues” tab and a “Preview” tab.

Now a taxon Wikidata item schema needs to be created. This is similar to the steps taken to create a new taxon Wikidata item (see [Creating a new Wikidata taxon item](#)).

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project showing Wikidata as the target Wikibase instance. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](#)

Choose the “Target Wikibase instance” which in this case is Wikidata as this is where the new item will be created.

Then press the “add item” button on the bottom lefthand side of OpenRefine.

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project showing the generated schema form. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](#)

This will generate a form where the schema for the new Wikidata items can be created.

The screenshot shows the 'Genus' item configuration in OpenRefine. The 'Terms' section contains two entries:

Property	Language	Value	Override if present	Action
Label	en	Genus	<input type="checkbox"/>	remove
Description	en	genus of Lepidoptera	<input type="checkbox"/>	remove

Below the terms is the 'Statements' section, which currently shows 'no statements added' and a '+ add statement' button.

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project showing the addition of Wikidata labels and descriptions in the schema. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](#)

Drag the genus column, which should still contain only those cells where OpenRefine has been unstructured to create new items, to the “type item or drag reconciled column” box.

Then press “add term” in blue on the righthand side of OpenRefine. Add both the language of the label as well as a label for the new item. In this case the language chosen is English and the label will also be the genus name, so the reconciled genus column can again be used.

Then press “add term” again and add the language and a description for the new item. In this case again English is chosen and a general description for all the new items to be created is added.

Then press “add statement” at the bottom righthand side of OpenRefine. It is here that the statements to be added to the new item can be created.

The screenshot shows the 'Statements' panel for a new Wikidata item. It lists four statements to be added:

Property	Value	References	Actions
instance of	taxon	1 reference	remove, configure, add qualifier
stated in	Biota of New Zealand	1 reference	remove, add, add reference, add value
taxon name	Genus	1 reference	remove, configure, add qualifier, add reference, add value
taxon rank	genus	1 reference	remove, configure, add qualifier, add reference, add value
parent taxon	Family	0 references	remove, configure

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project showing the addition of statements intended to be added to the new Wikidata item. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](#)

The first statement to be added uses the Wikidata property “instance of” [P31](#) and then the QID value of “taxon” [Q16521](#). Continue to add statements for each of the required data elements for a new taxon item using the data model shown below for guidance.

Minimum taxon item data model

Following the minimum data model for a taxon item, the schema will need to generate the following statements in Wikidata:

[P31](#) instance of [Q16521](#) taxon

[P225](#) taxon name [reconciled genus column]

[P105](#) taxon rank [Q34740](#) genus

[P171](#) parent taxon [reconciled family column]

Referencing

▼ 1 reference

stated in	Biota of New Zealand
Biota of New Zealand ID	de4c584d-6788-494f-a47c-4adc64fc042b
retrieved	5 October 2025

Screenshot of an example of a reference statement on a Wikidata item. Wikimedia Foundation. [CC BY-SA 4.0](#)

Each of the newly created statements in this schema should also be referenced. Ideally the Biota of New Zealand website and the Biota of New Zealand identifier for the genus will be used as the reference supporting the addition of this data.

The screenshot shows the OpenRefine interface for editing a Wikidata statement. The statement is 'instance of' with the value 'taxon'. A dropdown menu is open showing '1 references'. The references are:

- stated in: Biota of New Zealand
- Biota of New Zealand ID: Nameld
- retrieved: 2025-10-05

Each reference has a 'remove' button. There are also buttons for '+ add', '+ add reference', and '+ add value'.

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project showing the addition of a reference to be added to a statement in the new Wikidata item. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](#)

A reference is added to the schema in a similar manner as the proposed statements. Press “add reference” on the righthand side of OpenRefine under a statement. Then use either the “stated in” [P248](#) property or “reference URL” property [P854](#) to add the Wikidata for or URL link to the source of the data being added to Wikidata. Note that in order to add the Biota of New Zealand ID value to the reference a column containing this data should exist in the OpenRefine project. It is also important to add the date the data was retrieved to the reference.

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project showing how the reference can be copied. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](#)

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project showing the paste reference option. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](#)

Once the reference for the statement has been created, OpenRefine allows for this reference to be copied and reused on other schema statements. Press “copy” in blue found under the reference and then paste that reference onto the below statements by clicking “paste reference” on the righthand side of OpenRefine.

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project issues tab. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](#)

Once the schema is complete with statements added for all the required parts of the taxon data model, the issues tab provided by OpenRefine should be checked. OpenRefine will warn users if new Wikidata items are to be created and will also add warnings for other possible issues. If possible, issues raised should be resolved prior to the upload of data to Wikidata.

[Austrotortrix \(new item\)](#)

Label (do not override)	Austrotortrix (English)
Description (do not override)	genus of Lepidoptera (English)
taxon rank (P105)	genus (Q34740) ▶ 1 references
taxon name (P225)	Austrotortrix ▶ 1 references
Biota of New Zealand ID (P12292)	03a9cfb2-09ad-4b27-a4b3-662667bed8b9 ▶ 1 references
parent taxon (P171)	Tortricidae (Q28953) ▶ 1 references
instance of (P31)	taxon (Q16521) ▶ 1 references

Screenshot of an OpenRefine preview tab showing an example of the proposed edits. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](#)

The Preview tab should also be checked. This will give a summary of the proposed edits to a selection of new or existing Wikidata items.

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project showing the selection of Upload edits to Wikibase. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](#)

Once satisfied that the schema is complete and there are no outstanding issues to be resolved, the upload of data to Wikidata can commence by pressing the down arrow of the Extensions Wikibase tab and selecting “Upload edits to Wikibase...”

Wikidata account

Logging in to [Wikidata](#) lets you upload edits directly from OpenRefine.

You are encouraged to login with [bot passwords](#), see this [wiki page](#) to learn how to get one.

Username

Password

Remember me [?](#)

You can also [login with your owner-only consumer](#).

Close

Log in

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project showing the requirement to log into Wikidata prior to creating Wikidata items and uploading edits. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](#)

Log into Wikidata with your username and password. In the above example the author's Wikidata user name and password are shown.

Upload edits to Wikidata

You are about to upload 9 edits to [Wikidata](#). Please check them carefully. Large edit batches should be submitted for [bot review](#) first.

[?](#)

This edit batch will create new Wikidata items.

Please make sure that these items do not exist yet and are [suitable for inclusion in Wikidata](#).

Locate rows
9

You are logged in as: [Ambrosia10](#).

summary

maxlag Must be a positive integer. Leave this to the default value unless you know [how maxlag works](#).

Cancel

Upload edits

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project showing the uploading of edits to Wikidata by OpenRefine. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](#)

OpenRefine will then give a final warning that edits are about to be uploaded to Wikidata. Large edit batches should be submitted for bot review as the Wikidata community wants to ensure the quality of data in Wikidata.

Ensure to give a summary of the types of edits the OpenRefine batch upload will be doing. In this case OpenRefine will create new taxon Wikidata items for Lepidoptera genera.

Then press “upload edits” and OpenRefine will edit Wikidata on behalf of the editor, generating new items with the label, description, statements and references that have been created using OpenRefine.

Adding Biota of New Zealand ID to Wikidata

Screenshot of Wikidata showing the Biota of New Zealand ID for a taxon with a reference. Wikimedia Foundation. [CC BY-SA 4.0](#)

Now the relevant portions of the Biota of New Zealand lepidoptera genera dataset have been reconciled against existing or newly created Wikidata items, it is possible to add the Biota of New Zealand ID to all the reconciled Wikidata items in bulk.

First, to ensure all appropriate rows of the reconciled Genus column are able to be selected, clear all previously created judgements and facets from the OpenRefine project. If needed, keep or create judgements or facets that remove the unwanted data.

 OpenRefine Lepidoptera genera BiotaOfNZ tsv [Permalink](#)

The screenshot shows the OpenRefine interface. At the top, it says "Facet / Filter" and "Undo / Redo 195 / 195". Below that are buttons for "Refresh", "Reset all", and "Remove all". The main facet is titled "Genus: judgment" and shows "3 choices Sort by: name count". The choices are: "(blank) 4", "matched 747" (highlighted in orange), and "none 3". There is an "exclude" button next to the "matched" choice. Below the facet is a "Facet by choice counts" link. The main table shows "747 matching rows (754 total)" and "Show as: rows records". The table has columns for "Genus" and "Species". The Genus column lists: Sphenarches, Vogtia, Tachyptilia, Sperchia, Tortrix, and Ambhia. Each row has a "Choose new match" link.

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project showing the results of a facet by judgement on a mostly reconciled Genus column. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](#)

In the above example there are 7 rows of data that have either a blank Genus cell or a cell where the data is inappropriate to be included in the upload. By faceting the Genus column by reconciliation judgement all Genus cells that have been successfully reconciled against Wikidata can be worked on.

The next step is to create a new schema for the addition of the Biota of New Zealand ID to these reconciled taxon items. First delete the previous schema used to create the new items for missing genera. Then start to create the new schema.

The schema should include a statement giving the property for the Biota of New Zealand ID [P12292](#) along with the value attached to that property, that is the number string of the identifier. This statement should also be referenced giving the source of the information and the date that information was retrieved.

Target Wikibase instance: Wikidata

Start from an existing schema: Select... Save schema

[NameId](#) [NomenclaturalCode](#) [TaxonRank](#) [NameFull](#) [NamePart](#) [Kingdom](#) [Phylum](#) [Class](#) [Order](#) [Family](#) [Genus](#) [Species](#) [Authors](#) [author citation](#) [BasionymAuthors](#)
[CombinationAuthors](#) [ProtologueCitation](#) [ProtologueReferenceId](#) [YearOfPublication](#) [ProtologuePage](#) [Basionym](#) [BasionymNameId](#) [CurrentName](#) [CurrentNameId](#) [Synonyms](#) [Origin](#)
[Occurrence](#) [Wikibase editing results](#)

Genus remove

Terms
no labels, descriptions or aliases added add term

Statements

Biota of New Zealand NameId remove configure add qualifier

1 references

copy remove

stated in	Biota of New Zealand	remove
retrieved	2025-09-29	remove

add add reference add value add statement

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project showing a statement with the Biota of New Zealand ID and supporting reference. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](#)

Again the target Wikibase instance is Wikidata. The reconciled Genus column should be added to the “type item or drag reconciled column” box. The blue “add statement” text is clicked and the Biota of New Zealand ID property ([P12292](#)) is added to the property box. The “NameID” column, which lists all the appropriate Biota of New Zealand identifiers for the related taxa, is added to the value box and a reference is again created as outlined earlier in this document.

Issues

Before uploading this data to Wikidata, again the issues tab for the upload should be checked.

754 rows Schema * Issues 744 Preview Extensions Wikibase

Biota of New Zealand ID (P12292) added more than once on the same item. 30
This property is expected to be used at most once on each item but has been added multiple times on the same item, for instance on [Orocrambus \(Q5231762\)](#).

Biota of New Zealand ID (P12292) requires statement with property taxon name (P225). Locate rows 714
This property is expected to have another statement with property [taxon name \(P225\)](#) such as on item [Poecilasthena \(Q3007820\)](#). If the item already has statements with property [taxon name \(P225\)](#) in Wikidata, then this warning can be ignored.

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project showing the issues tab with two issues raised. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](#)

In this case the first warning is an issue that needs to be addressed by the editor. The second warning can be ignored as it can be expected that all the Wikidata items having the Biota of New Zealand ID added to them will have a statement giving the taxon name.

For the first warning it appears that multiple Biota of New Zealand IDs will be added to the same Wikidata item. The warning gives an example of a genus where this will be the case as a result of the upload of this data to Wikidata. In order to check the data and attempt to rectify this error, the following steps need to be taken.

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project showing a text facet on the Genus column. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

Go to the reconciled genus column, click the dropdown menu and select “Facet” and then “Text facet”.

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project showing the “Genus” box in the facet/filter tab on the lefthand side of OpenRefine. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

This will produce a “Genus” box in the facet/filter tab on the lefthand side of OpenRefine. Then press the “count” tab at the top of the box to the right of “Sort by:”. This will group together all the counts of genera names in the Genus column from highest to lowest. The issue raised relates to those genera that have a count higher than 1.

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project showing a genus with two potential Biota of New Zealand IDs. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](#)

Each of these issues should be worked through carefully with the editor making the decision whether it is appropriate to add a second Biota of New Zealand ID to the genus Wikidata item.

It is possible there is duplication within the Biota of New Zealand database. Biota of New Zealand identifiers relating to the same taxon may have been created in different datasets that have subsequently been combined into the Biota of New Zealand dataset. For example both the Manaaki Whenua - Landcare Research Fungi names dataset and the New Zealand Arthropod Collection dataset may contain information on the same genus thus giving two Biota of New Zealand identifiers that should be added to the appropriate Wikidata item. Although adding two identifiers will raise a constraint violation in Wikidata this may, in the judgement of the editor, be appropriate given the data contained in the Biota of New Zealand dataset.

Alternatively, this issue may have arisen as the Biota of New Zealand identifiers relate to a different taxon concept with the same taxon name. In this case care should be taken to ensure the correct Biota of New Zealand identifier is added to the Wikidata item for the appropriate taxonomic concept.

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project facet box in the facet/filter tab showing a facet by star. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](#)

Any Biota of New Zealand identifiers that, in the judgement of the editor, should not be added to the Wikidata item can be removed from the proposed upload by either starring or flagging the identifier row, then faceting by either the star or flag. By selecting only those rows that have not been starred or flagged editors can ensure they work on cells that have no issues.

Upload Biota of New Zealand ID

Once any issues with the proposed upload have been worked through and the editor is satisfied with the proposed upload, the editor should proceed with adding the Biota of New Zealand ID to appropriate Wikidata items.

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project showing the selection of “Upload edits to Wikibase...”. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](#)

To do this, press the down arrow of the Extensions Wikibase tab on the righthand side of OpenRefine and select “Upload edits to Wikibase...”

Wikidata account

Logging in to [Wikidata](#) lets you upload edits directly from OpenRefine.

You are encouraged to login with [bot passwords](#), see this [wiki page](#) to learn how to get one.

Username

Password

Remember me ⓘ

You can also [login with your owner-only consumer](#).

Close

Log in

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project showing the OpenRefine Wikidata login boxes. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](#)

Log into Wikidata with your username and password. Again the above example shows the username and obscured password for the writer of this documentation.

Upload edits to Wikidata

You are about to upload 714 edits to Wikidata. Please check them carefully. Large edit batches should be submitted for [bot review](#) first.

Biota of New Zealand ID (P12292) added more than once on the same item. 27

This property is expected to be used at most once on each item but has been added multiple times on the same item, for instance on [Orocrambus \(Q5231762\)](#).

Biota of New Zealand ID (P12292) requires statement with property taxon name (P225). 714

Locate rows

This property is expected to have another statement with property [taxon name \(P225\)](#) such as on item [Poecilasthena \(Q3007820\)](#). If the item already has statements with property [taxon name \(P225\)](#) in Wikidata, then this warning can be ignored.

You are logged in as: [Ambrosia10](#).

summary

maxlag Must be a positive integer. Leave this to the default value unless you know [how maxlag works](#).

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project showing the issues tab with two issues raised. OpenRefine. [CC BY 4.0](#)

The issues warnings previously dealt with will again appear. Add a summary of the type of edits this batch will undertake and then press the “Upload edits” button on the bottom righthand side of OpenRefine.

This will upload the Biota of New Zealand ID to all selected Wikidata items for lepidoptera genera. Now all the genera have been worked through, the editor can repeat the above workflow to add the Biota of New Zealand ID to appropriate species Wikidata items.

Helpful resources

OpenRefine documentation <https://openrefine.org/docs>

OpenRefine editing tutorial

https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Tools/OpenRefine/Editing/Tutorials/Basic_editing/en

OpenRefine editing video

<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Tools/OpenRefine/Editing/Tutorials/Video>

Wikidata query

Query for all Wikidata items with a Biota of New Zealand ID <https://w.wiki/HXA7>